

Analysis of Internal Marketing, Psychologic and Professional Practices as Factors of Employability Challenges in an Electronic Industry of Tijuana, Mexico

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Abstract – An investigation was made to evaluate the correlation analysis of the internal marketing process in higher education institutions and the evaluation of university professional practices focused on a prestigious higher education institution in the city of Tijuana, linked to the factor of employability in industrial activities in this border region with the United States of America (USA) of an electronic industry installed in this city. This analysis consisted of evaluating the processes of the implementation of the internal marketing process in an industrial company in the city of Tijuana, considered an industrial city and border area with the state of California, where a large number of commercial exchange activities are generated, and this State of the United States of America (USA) is very important in the economy of the USA. Also, was made an analysis about the principal physiological factors to obtain positive attitude and conscientization of operative workers to make its functions efficiently. In addition, the action of labor employability related to the professional internship programs of a prestigious educational institution in this northwestern region of the Mexican Republic was evaluated. These analyzes were carried out with statistical tests such as the Chi-Square test and Cronbach's alpha coefficient, to determine the relationship between the variables involved in this relevant scientific study. This investigation was made in 2022.

Keywords: Internal marketing, labor employability, professional practices, industrial activities

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of internal marketing in any type of activity is of great relevance for the development of activities efficiently, with which maximum efficiency can be obtained in the operational performance of operational personnel and other types of work positions (Nart et al, 2019). This relevant factor supports to a great extent to make workers aware of any work activity to apply their attitude, aptitudes, abilities, conduct and abilities; that have a positive effect on their operational performance and thus achieve their goals on a daily basis, in a

personal, work and educational way (Kanyurhi et al, 2016). In addition to this type of important aspect, this research evaluates the operational performance of students recently graduated or with a short period of graduation from a university in industrial activities of various types of manufacturing processes, with the aim of raising awareness among young people (Al-Borie, 2012; Contreras-Cueva et al, 2014). This is so that they made their functions consciously and thus be able to generate efficient actions in their work activities, which encourages them to obtain the desired and well-paid job economically. In this investigation were applied some physiological strategies were applied convince to operative workers to make its functions at optimal manner (Grilo et al, 2014).

1.1 Internal Marketing in the Tijuana Industry

It is a process applied in any work activity to make workers aware that they can feel identified with a brand or company name, whether commercial or industrial, with the aim of achieving the proposed productivity and quality goals (Araque et al, 2017). This is based on cordial and effective communication actions, as well as the development of courses that promote the impact of the application of internal marketing in all companies, observing the positive effect on the generation of solid sales. In accordance with the aforementioned (Martín-Villarroya et al, 2017), that lead to all the people of any company receiving productivity and quality bonuses, based on sales, as is made with profits in the Mexican Republic and other types of end-of-year bonuses, or of another type of event promoted by the management personnel of the companies. Internal marketing helps to generate motivation in the personnel of each company, where some strategies that are mentioned below are contemplated (Cialdini, 2015):

- a) It is necessary to know the workers (abilities, skills, incompetence, ideas and thoughts; to be able to support them in the best way and thus optimally develop their functions.
- b) The goals to be achieved must be defined in a concrete way and the appropriate methods and techniques must be applied to obtain maximum operational efficiency, and thereby inspire them with prizes and economic bonuses for productivity and quality on a constant basis.
- c) Support your operating personnel in any area to continue in the formation of knowledge, with training courses and be trained workers for any activity.
- d) Recreational activities can be included that allow the integration of the work team in harmony and cordiality, so that the operating personnel feel part of the team, such as active breaks with music and short-term exercise.

The information mentioned above is showed in Figure 1.

Fig -1: Motivation factors for operating personnel in companies

1.2 Professional practices and their relationship with labor employability in Tijuana

It is a relevant aspect in the formation of the attitude, aptitudes, capacities and abilities of students about to enter and recently graduated, who do not have work experience and must carry out professional practices in commercial or industrial companies of any type of work activity. Figure 2 represents the main factors involved in professional practice activities, which are analyzed in order to develop them in the most optimal way, and thereby obtain maximum efficiency in the training of human resources (Krudthong, 2017). This figure illustrates the relationship of the main important aspects of professional practices, mentioning the first as the link with the productive sector (public (governmental) and private (commercial and industrial) (Arias et al, 2018). The second aspect is the training of human resources, which higher educational institutions (HEIs), being the main public and private universities, technological institutes and research centers (Romero et al, 2015). This is done with the objective to apply specialized strategies, which support the training of students, who, upon graduation, are prepared to contribute to solving problematic situations in industries of the commercial and industrial sector and government institutions, as well as to apply continuous improvement constantly (Reza et al, 2019).

Fig -2: Principal aspects of the professional practices

1.3 Relationship of internal marketing with psychological factors in industries

One of the relevant aspects that relate to the internal marketing of psychology is the persuasion action, which consists of having the tolerance, patience and prudence, to reach agreements between people, where it is desired that all people participate at the same time. rhythm and achieve the proposed goals (Karatepe, 2011). The objective of this type of relationship is to achieve the conviction of the workers in the operational areas of commercial or industrial companies, where the executive, managerial and supervisory personnel (Backhoff et al, 2018). They are in charge of developing the methods and techniques of the activities to be carried out, as well as generating an adequate, cordial communication that is attached to the functions of the operational personnel. According to the psychologist Robert Cialdini, who wrote the book "The Psychology of Persuasion", he suggests that six basic principles should be evaluated that can support the convincing process, managing to stimulate the neural system (Kajalo et al, 2015). These principles are explained below:

- a) Principle of Reciprocity. It represents the action of appreciation of appropriate behaviors of people, towards us, where the effect of being able to return the favors received is contemplated. According to the writer José Carlos León in his book "Change Marketers: The company as a change agent", he states that, in an analysis carried out in restaurants, at the time of delivering the purchase receipt to customers with a sweet or detail of the business, tips were increased tips.
- b) Principle of Scarcity. It indicates that the actions to be carried out are for a certain period, where people are convinced to develop their functions as part of an improvement or emergency momentarily.
- c) Principle of Authority. This aspect is part of the action of involving information or experts in the activities to be carried out, with the aim of considering that the activities to be carried out are of vital importance and can be achieved easily and simply.

d) Principle of Coherence. Prepare an evaluation that the actions that you want to carry out are adequately communicated, and that each activity carried out can still generate a minor effect, and that the people who carry them out are recognized.

e) Principle of Social Approval. It consists of generating the action that people feel integrated into a work team, with which an efficient performance of them can be obtained.

f) Principle of Sympathy. It represents the action of the executive staff, management; and supervision are empathetic with the workers in operational areas, as well as having a pleasant and attractive work environment, which leads to made activities in a harmonious, cordial manner and with great effort.

The six principles explained are represented in figure 3.

Fig -3:Basic Principals to apply the persuasion action

1.4 Tijuana Electronics Industry

This type of industry is very important worldwide, where a wide variety of electronic products are manufactured that are widely used in all parts of the world, and are widely used by people of any age. In this currently high-tech industry, household appliances (fans, vacuum cleaners, water heaters, stoves, blenders and refrigerators, mainly), communication equipment (computers, internet connection equipment, tablets, cell phones and televisions, essentially), security equipment (alarms and object and person detection equipment) and other types of electronic equipment, which include advanced technology and are widely applied in daily life. In the city of Tijuana, it is considered that there are around 60% of this type of industry out of a total of 650 that are installed (AMT, 2022).

2. METHODOLOGY

An investigation was elaborated to correlate the parameters of internal marketing, psychological factors and development of professional practices; with the objective of achieving the conviction of the workers of the operational areas to elaborate their functions in an optimal way and with this to achieve the goals proposed in each commercial or industrial company. For this scientific study, the following operations were elaborated:

- a) Analysis of level of awareness of operational personnel.
- b) Evaluation of operative level of expert personnel and practitioners.
- c) Analysis of productivity and quality.

3. RESULTS

This investigative analysis generated relevant information based on the activities developed in this scientific study, managing to improve the attitude of the operational personnel of the evaluated industry, being observed in the following stages of this investigative analysis.

3.1 Awareness level analysis

In this section of the scientific study was made to determine the level of awareness of workers, where figure 4 shows the quantity of operative workers and its awareness level, represented by the percentage (%), where was observed that the expert workers (950) from total of workers (1000 as maximum quantity in a period of the year (April to July of 2022)) were more than practitioners (50). This figure 4 shows by periods the correlation between practitioners and expert people that was working in the industry where was made the investigation. This was relevant to determine the strategic of internal marketing and physiological principles mentioned above to convince to workers of manufacturing areas and generates the maximum operative yielding and with this the maximum productivity and quality levels.

PP. Practitioners People; EP. Expert People

Fig -4:Evaluation of awareness of operative personnel of electronics industry evaluated (2022)

3.2 Operational efficacy analysis

This part of the investigation was made to determine the operative efficiency, where was illustrated in the table 1 the difference between expert workers and practitioners recently graduated or who are going to graduate from a prestigious university in this northwestern region of the Mexican Republic. This led to generating internal marketing strategies and applying the six basic principles of persuasion to the operating personnel of the industrial company where this investigation was made. Table 1 represents the evaluation in 2022 from January to December, where was illustrated the low operative efficacy in the two first months of the investigation. From the third month was increased, illustrating the application of internal marketing and physiological basic principles of the persuasion action. The rest of the period of 2022 was increased the operative efficacy of the workers (expert and practitioners), where was reached the goals of productivity and quality of the attitude of workers.

Table -1: Analysis of operative efficacy of works of an electronic industry (2022)

Parameters	Quantity of Workers		Operative Efficacy, %	
	Expert People	Practitioners	Expert People	Practitioners
January	688	62	87	45
February	719	79	89	48
March	787	83	83	56
April	815	76	85	59
May	856	80	79	62
June	900	97	81	64
July	900	100	80	69
August	883	85	86	70
September	852	79	88	73
October	836	71	76	67
November	744	68	79	69
December	698	56	83	78

3.3 Evaluation of productivity and quality indices

This evaluation was made to determine in base of the good attitude and capacitation of expert personnel and practitioners, was analyzed the productivity and quality levels, where was observed in table 2 the relation without and with strategies of internal marketing and phycological basic principles about the persuasion action to convince workers of operativity activities to make its functions as efficient manner. The strategies of internal marketing and physiological principles mentioned above were relevant to each the goals proposed every week and obtain the maximum productivity and quality levels, where were evaluated by diverse periods, which was made this important investigation. This was made of interesting to directive and manager people who was put attention to maintain the ideal conditions to workers of the manufacturing people and convince to make its functions as optimal manner. In table 2 is showed the increase conforms was advanced this investigation in the electronics industry mentioned above and was reach the goals with good attitude of

workers that were in the industrial processes. Workers received by some periods some bonus of productivity and quality, and were working with major illusion.

Table -2:Evaluation of productivity and quality levels in the electronic industry analyzed (2022)

Parameters	Productivity, %		Quality, %	
	Expert People	Practitioners	Expert People	Practitioners
January	78	43	89	32
February	83	46	94	37
March	80	49	96	39
April	84	54	98	46
May	85	59	92	57
June	89	63	89	68
July	92	60	88	79
August	89	58	94	86
September	95	68	96	90
October	97	75	97	85
November	89	79	94	88
December	93	81	96	89

4. CONCLUSIONS

This investigation was made from determining the basic strategies of internal marketing and physiological principles that have a positive effect in the attitude if workers to obtain the goals proposed by periods, where during this investigation and forever. This was relevant, because the physiological principles were a great impact in the convincement of operative people and were observed to make its functions as efficacy manner. These interesting thematic contents are very important in each activity that are operative persons, where are necessary apply this type strategies of internal marketing and physiological principles, to convince to workers to feel as part of the electronics industry evaluated and have more operative yielding every day and with this, maximum productivity and quality levels. Also, this scientific study can be applied to other type of are in this same industry, or in other type of industry, where was installed in this northwest region of the Mexican Republic and obtain the best results in the production of manufacturing processes.

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